

UNIVERSITY OF THE ARTS LONDON

*Transforming structured descriptions to visual
representations. An automated visualization
of historical bookbinding structures*

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Volume 2 - Appendices

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Appendix A. Human memory system

Data perceived through our senses (sight, hearing, smell, touch, taste) is stored in the sensory memory for a very short length of time (between 200 and 500 milliseconds). Usually this information is passed on to our working memory only if the conscious mind activates an attention behaviour (however, some sensed data can linger for longer in an unconscious manner⁵⁰²). In our working memory, different kinds of information (visuospatial, auditory, episodic) are processed by a series of subsidiary systems coordinated by an attentive central executive. It is in the working memory that we process information for then discard it or record it in the long-term memory system for later retrieval.⁵⁰³

In our working memory, information dissipates in a matter of seconds if not rehearsed, and its capacity is rather limited. Studies suggest that we can hold in our working memory only around seven chunks of information. This limit seems to be physiological, as it does not seem to change with expertise. Expert minds, in fact, are only apparently capable of holding greater amounts of information in their working memory buffer: they are capable of developing increasingly complex representations of familiar patterns with direct access to data previously encoded in the long-term memory system, thus chunking more familiar and related data within each slot available. Unfamiliar patterns, or random data limit the chunking capacities even of expert minds.⁵⁰⁴

Once processed and retained, information can be encoded into the long-term memory system, where it is stored for hours, days, or even a lifetime — e.g. pro-

⁵⁰². Brandimonte *et al.* 1992a; Brandimonte *et al.* 1992b; Brandimonte & Gerbino 1996.

⁵⁰³. Baddeley & Hitch 1974; Baddeley 1992; Baddeley 2000; Baddeley 2007; Alloway & Alloway 2012; Baddeley 2013.

⁵⁰⁴. Miller 1956; Cowan 2001; Saaty & Ozdemir 2003; Gobet & Clarkson 2004; Ericsson & Moxley 2012.

Figure 1. A model of the human memory system (after Baddeley & Hitch 1974; Baddeley 1992; Baddeley 2000; Baddeley 2007; Alloway & Alloway 2012; Baddeley 2013). Sensed data is processed in the sensory memory and, through attention, is passed on to the working memory system, which can store a limited amount of information for a limited amount of time before it is discarded or recorded in the long-term memory system. Our cognitive capabilities are limited by the capacity of our working memory.

cedural and semantic knowledge — and from where it can be retrieved, with more or less facility depending on the frequency in which a piece of information needs to be accessed: the more frequent the use, the easier and quicker the retrieval is.

Amongst the non-declarative kinds of long-term memory, an important phenomenon is that of *priming*. This refers to the implicit memory effect by which, exposure to a stimulus has measurable effects on the response to a later stimulus. This is of particular interest when considering visual stimuli. Once we have seen a visual pattern of some kind, it becomes much easier and quicker for our brain to identify it at a later appearance, and this priming effects can linger for minutes, or even hours. This means that recognition of visual patterns is much easier if the subjects are primed by visually similar images. This effect is strictly image-dependent and not based on high-level semantic information, but it can occur even if information is not consciously perceived.⁵⁰⁵

⁵⁰⁵. Ware 2013.

Appendix B. Shape library

This appendix contains the diagrams for the various components — and their possible variations — for each bookbinding structure.

Each section begins with the graph schema for the relevant structure and its description/transformation. As covered in §6.2.1, graph schemas are a graphical representation of the information involved in each bookbinding structure description and transformation. At a glance, the reader can appreciate the complexity of a description/transformation, and graph schemas can also be followed, step by step, each node adding a new piece of information, each choice branching in parallel information paths. Graph schemas present all the information needed for a description/transformation in one page (or series of related pages for very complex structures).

Each graph schema is followed by a series of diagrams that can be generated from the information that it contains. All the diagrams shown have been automatically generated from XML descriptions. Titles and labels are used to relate the diagrams and their elements to nodes in the graph schema.

This appendix is subdivided into sections, one for each bookbinding structure, as follows: (i) page markers, (ii) board markers, (ii) bookmarks, (iv) endleaves, (v) sewing, (vi) boards, (vii) spine shape, (viii) spine lining, (ix) endbands, (x) coverings, (xi) furniture - fastenings

Page markers

Page markers are those tabs attached to the edges of leaves in a book to indicate important places in the text. See §7.2.1.

PAGE MARKERS

STRAIGHT - FORE-EDGE

FOLDED & KNOTTED - HEAD

FOLDED - TAIL

Board markers

Board markers are lengths of animal skin pasted to the inside of the board, projecting from the edge and most probably used as bookmarks. See §7.2.1.

BOARD MARKERS

UNDER TURNIN - FORE-EDGE LEFT

OVER TURNIN - FORE-EDGE RIGHT

Bookmarks

A bookmark is a device used to mark temporarily particular leaves or passages of a book; its formation can range from simple lengths of thread or textile ribbon to multiple elements attached to bars or disks fixed to an endband. See §7.2.1.

BOOKMARK GRAPH SCHEMA

BOOKMARKS (COMPOUND) - I

PRIMARY: SPAN I

SECONDARY: KNOTTED DOUBLE LENGTH

PRIMARY: SPAN I

SECONDARY: KNOTTED SINGLE LENGTH

BOOKMARKS (COMPOUND) - 2

PRIMARY: SPAN I

SECONDARY: HITCHED DOUBLE LENGTH

PRIMARY: SPAN I

SECONDARY: SEWING SINGLE LENGTH

BOOKMARKS (COMPOUND) - 3

PRIMARY: SPAN I
SECONDARY: PLAITED

PRIMARY: SPAN I
SECONDARY: PLIED

BOOKMARKS (COMPOUND) - 4

PRIMARY: SPAN 2

SECONDARY: KNOTTED SINGLE LENGTH

PRIMARY: MULTIPLE SPAN

SECONDARY: KNOTTED SINGLE LENGTH

BOOKMARKS (COMPOUND) - 5

PRIMARY: TWISTED CLOSED LOOP

SECONDARY: KNOTTED DOUBLE LENGTH

Endleaves

Endleaves are all the groups of leaves found at each side of a bookblock and are intended to give protection to the text leaves. They come in two basic types: those added by the binder before the book is sewn (separate endleaves) and blank leaves at the front and/or the back of the textblock (integral endleaves) which are used as endleaves, and may or may not also be pasted to the boards as pastedowns, even though they form part of text gatherings. Separate endleaves and integral endleaves can be combined at either the left or right ends of the textblock, and the endleaves at left and right can be made up differently. See §7.1.

ENDLEAVES - I

INTEGRAL

SEPARATE - FOLD

SEWN

SEPARATE - GUARD

ENDLEAVES - 2

SEPARATE - ENDLEAF HOOK (NOT DOUBLE)

SEPARATE - ENDLEAF HOOK (DOUBLE)

SEPARATE - TEXT HOOK (NOT DOUBLE)

SEPARATE - TEXT HOOK (DOUBLE)

ENDLEAVES - 3

SEPARATE - OUTSIDE HOOK

SEPARATE - SINGLE LEAF

Sewing

Sewing indicates the process through which the sections or leaves of a book are secured by means of thread, thus forming a consecutive and permanent unit. The basic description element of each sewing is the sewing station, i.e. the individual structural point on the spine-fold used in the creation of the book structure. See §7.2.2.

SEWING GRAPH SCHEMA I

SEWING - I

(MEASUREMENTS IN MM)

SEWING - 2

Current sewing (type: allAlong)

Previous sewing

SEWING - 3

PREPARATION

PIERCED HOLE

vNICK

SINGLE KNIFE CUT

UNSUPPORTED SEWING - TWO NEEDLE

UNSUPPORTED SEWING - SINGLE SEQUENCE

SEWING - 4

UNSUPPORTED SEWING - DOUBLE SEQUENCE

SUPPORTED SEWING - SINGLE

CHANGE-OVER ST.: KETTLESTITCH

SUPPORTED SEWING - DOUBLE

Boards

The wood, pasted paper, single- or multiple-ply sheets, or other material, used for the covers of bound books to protect the leaves. Boards are usually used in pairs and they never extend around the spine of the book. See §7.2.3.

BOARDS - I

CENTRE BEVELS

BOARDS - 2

INTERNAL BEVELS

BOARDS - 3

CLASP BEVELS

BOARDS - 4

CUSHION

PERIPHERAL CUSHION

(ENDBAND CORE)
SEWN & RECESSED

BOARDS - 5

EDGE TREATMENT

FORE-EDGE CORNER

BOARDS - 6

SPINE CORNER

JOINT SHAPE ANGLED

JOINT SHAPE ACUTE

Spine shape

The schema describes the shape of the spine of the bookblock in an approximate and categorized manner distinguishing between its degree of roundness (flat, slight round, round, heavy round) or the shape of its joints (flat, slight, quadrant, angled, square, acute). This allows inputting a record of the shape of the spine in the database, and to then be able, for example, to search for different values of roundness for bookblock spines. See §7.2.4.

SPINE GRAPH SCHEMA

SPINE: SHAPE & JOINTS - I

SHAPE: FLAT

JOINTS: NONE/FLAT

SHAPE: SLIGHT ROUND

JOINTS: SLIGHT

SHAPE: ROUND

JOINTS: QUADRANT

SPINE: SHAPE & JOINTS - 2

SHAPE: HEAVY ROUND

JOINTS: ANGLED

SHAPE: ROUND

JOINTS: SQUARE

SHAPE: ROUND

JOINTS: ACUTE

Spine lining

The spine lining is composed of one or a series of pieces of sheet material placed on the spine of the assembled bookblock as reinforcement, and either adhered to it or held in place without adhesive. See §7.2.4.

SPINE LINING - I

TYPE: OVERALL

SPINE LINING - 2

TYPE: TRANSVERSE

PASTED TO FLYLEAF

LOCATION: SELECTED

SPINE LINING - 3

TYPE: COMB

PASTED INSIDE BOARDS

LOCATION: ALL

SPINE LINING - 4

TYPE: PANEL

LOCATION: ALL

SPINE LINING - 4

TYPE: PATCH

LOCATION: SELECTED

SPINE LINING - 6

TYPE: CONTINUOUS

LOCATION: ALL

SPINE LINING - 7

TYPE: TRANSVERSE

FREE

LOCATION: ALL

Endbands

Endbands are cores sewn or pasted across the head and tail of a bookblock spine. When sewn, these are attached to the bookblock by a primary sewing through the fold of the gatherings which loops around the core. When pasted, these are essentially transverse spine lining attached to the head and tail panels. See §7.2.5.

ENDBANDS - I

SEWN

ENDBANDS - 2

NO BEAD

FRONT BEAD

ENDBANDS - 3

NO FRONT BEAD

REVERSING TWIST

ENDBANDS - 4

GREEK SINGLE CORE

GREEK DOUBLE CORE

ENDBANDS - 5

WARPS ONLY

TIEDOWNS

ENDBANDS - 6

BOARD ATTACHMENT - SEWN

BOARD ATTACHMENT - SEWN AND RECESSED

BOARD ATTACHMENT - LACED

ENDBANDS - 7

BOARD ATTACHMENT - ADHERED

BOARD ATTACHMENT - CUT AT JOINT

ENDBANDS - 8

CROWNING CORE - SEWN WITH PRIMARY

CROWNING CORE - SEWN WITH SECONDARY

ENDBANDS - 9

STUCK-ON

ENDBANDS - IO

FOLDED

NOT PASTED
ON BOARDS

NOT FOLDED

ENDBANDS - II

PASTED INSIDE BOARDS

ABOVE

FRONT

BACK

ENDBANDS - I2

PASTED OUTSIDE BOARDS

ABOVE

FRONT

BACK

Coverings

The term *covering* indicates those materials put over a book, with the effect of protecting it. The schema distinguishes between four main kinds of coverings (guard, drawn-on, case, and over-in-boards) indicating rather different constructions. The two more simple types, guard and drawn-on, are not further specified by other parameters. Case and over-in-boards covers, instead, are further specified by means of a range of typologies and parameters. Because of the diversity in features and the wide range of options, the graph schema is presented here as divided in three related schemas: guard and drawn-on together, over-in-board, and case covering respectively. See §7.2.6.

COVERING GRAPH SCHEMA - DRAWN-ON/GUARD

COVERING - I

DRAWN-ON

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - 2

GUARD

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - 3

OVER IN BOARD - FULL

CAP DETAIL:
STRAIGHT

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - 4

OVER IN BOARD - HALF

CAP DETAIL:
STRAIGHT

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - 5

OVER IN BOARD - HALF

CAP DETAIL:
STRAIGHT

CROSS SECTION

WITH
PARCHMENT
TIPS

OUTER VIEW

WITH PARCHMENT
TIPS

INNER VIEW

WITH PARCHMENT
TIPS

COVERING - 6

GROOVED JOINT

STEPPED JOINT

TIGHT JOINT

STRAIGHT CAP

PULLED-OVER CAP

COVERING - 7

COVERING - 8

CAPCORE

LAPPED FORE-EDGE OVER

LAPPED HEAD & TAIL OVER

LAPPED MIXED

TONGUED MITRE

COVERING - 9

BUTT MITRE

OPEN MITRE

CLOCKWISE

ANTI-CLOCKWISE

COVERING - IO

CASE - ADHESIVE - ONE PIECE

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - II

CASE - ADHESIVE - THREE PIECE (CUT FLUSH)

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - I2

CASE - ADHESIVE - THREE PIECE (TURNED IN)

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - I3

CASE - ADHESIVE - BOARD COVER SPINE INFILL

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - I4

CASE - LACE ATTACHED - LIMP LACED (ENDBAND SLIPS)

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - I5

CASE - LACE ATTACHED - COVER LINING

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

OUTER VIEW

COVERING - I6

CASE - LACE ATTACHED - BOARDS (SUPPORT SLIPS)

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

INNER VIEW

COVERING - I7

CASE - LACE ATTACHED - TACKETED (LOOP)

TACKET DETAIL

CROSS SECTION

LOC. SEWING

OUTER VIEW

LOC. SEWING

INNER VIEW

LOC. ENDBAND

INDIVIDUAL REINF.

COVERING - I8

CASE - LACE ATTACHED - TACKETED (SALTIRE)

TACKET DETAIL

CROSS SECTION

LOC. ENDBAND

SINGLE STATION REINF.

OUTER VIEW

LOC. ENDBAND

OUTER VIEW

LOC. SEWING

SINGLE STATION REINF.

COVERING - 19

CASE - LACE ATTACHED - TACKETED (TRANSVERSE TWISTED)

TACKET DETAIL

CROSS SECTION

OUTER VIEW

LOC. SEWING -
WHOLESPINE REINF.

INNER VIEW

COVERING - 20

CASE - LACE ATTACHED - TACKETED (TRANSVERSE)

TACKET DETAIL

CROSS SECTION

LAPPED CORNER

LOCKED CORNER

EDGE TREATMENT:
CUT

EDGE TREATMENT:
TURNED IN

GROOVED JOINT

SPINE CREASE

WITHOUT JOINT CREASE

SPINE CREASE

WITH JOINT CREASE

COVERING - 2I

CASE - EXTERNAL SUPPORTS

OUTER VIEW

CASE - LONGSTITCH

OUTER VIEW

Furniture - fastenings

Furniture is the set of hardware that can be attached to a binding, usually with a protective, but also often decorative, function; this includes fastenings used to hold a book shut when not in use. Furniture include: (i) articulated metal spine, (ii) bosses, (iii) corners, (iv) full covers, (v) plates, (vi) ties, (vii) catchplates, (viii) clasps, (ix) pins, (x) straps, (xi) strap collars, (xii) and strap plates. Items *vii* to *xii* can be grouped as fastening parts. These are described in sufficient detail in the schema and their descriptions can be turned into useful visualizations. Items *i* to *vi*, instead, are only named by their generic name — e.g. boss or tie — leaving too much indeterminateness for the generation of meaningful visualizations. See §7.2.7.

FURNITURE (FASTENINGS) - I

EDGE
FASTENED PIN

STIRRUP RING

TRIPLE BRAIDED
SRAP

UNDER PASTEDOWN

SIDE
SIMPLE PIN

STIRRUP RING

DOUBLE BRAIDED
SRAP

THROUGH PASTEDOWN

FURNITURE (FASTENINGS) - 2

ROLLER-ROUND BAR

SIMPLE HOOK

FLAT STRAP

RAISED LIP

FOLDED HOOK

FLAT STRAP

STRAP PLATE

FURNITURE (FASTENINGS) - 3

EDGE
SIMPLE PIN

PIERCED FLAT STRAP

UNDER PASTEDOWN

THROUGH PASTEDOWN

BENT AND SLOTTED

FOLDED HOOK

FLAT STRAP

STRAP PLATE

Appendix C. Coding example: endleaves

This appendix contains, as an example from the various transformation scenarios written for this project, the coding for endleaf structure visualizations.

For each transformation, there is an XSLT stylesheet that takes the information relative to a binding structure and generates an SVG visualization. The few elements of the visualizations that could be predefined and utilized where needed are defined in a master SVG file, from which they are called by the XSLT stylesheet; the SVG master also contains the code for the various filters applicable when needed to the diagram elements, e.g. to visualize uncertainty or imprecision. The appearance of lines and other graphical elements is ruled by classes defined within a Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)⁵⁰⁶ file.

This appendix is subdivided into three sections: the XSLT stylesheet, the SVG master, and the CSS stylesheet for endleaf transformations. See §7.1.

⁵⁰⁶. CSS is a style sheet language used for describing the look and formatting of documents written in a markup language. Etemad 2011.

Endleaf XSLT

This section contains the XSLT coding written for this project to generate endleaf diagrams.

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>

<xsl:stylesheet xmlns:xsl="http://www.w3.org/1999/XSL/Transform"
  xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" xmlns:svg="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg"

  xmlns:lig="http://www.ligatus.org.uk/stcatherines/sites/ligatus.org.uk.stcather-
ines/files/basic-1.8_0.xsd"
  xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink" xmlns:dict="www.mydict.my"
  exclude-result-prefixes="xs svg xlink lig dict" version="2.0">

  <xsl:output method="xml" indent="yes" encoding="utf-8" doctype-public="-//W3C//DTD
SVG 1.1//EN"
    doctype-system="http://www.w3.org/Graphics/SVG/1.1/DTD/svg11.dtd" stan-
dalone="no"
    xpath-default-namespace="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" exclude-result-pre-
fixes="xlink"
    include-content-type="no"/>

  <xsl:variable name="shelfmark" select="//bibliographical/shelfmark"/>
  <xsl:variable name="fileref" select="tokenize(replace($shelfmark, '/', '.'),
'\.')

```

```

        <xsl:processing-instruction name="xml-stylesheet">
            <xsl:text>href="../../../../GitHub/XSLTransformations/Endleaves/CSS/style.css"&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:text>type="text/css"</xsl:text>
        </xsl:processing-instruction>
        <xsl:text>&#10;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:comment>
            <xsl:text>SVG file generated on: </xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="format-dateTime(current-dateTime(), '[D][M][Nn] [Y] at [H]:[m]:[s]')"/>
            <xsl:text> using </xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="system-property('xsl:product-name')"/>
            <xsl:text> version </xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="system-property('xsl:product-version')"/>
        </xsl:comment>
        <xsl:text>&#10;</xsl:text>
        <svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
            version="1.1" x="0" y="0" width="420mm" height="297mm"
            viewBox="0 0 420 297"
            preserveAspectRatio="xMidYMid meet">
            <title>Left endleaves of book: <xsl:value-of select="$shelfmark"/></title>
            <xsl:copy-of
                select="document('../SVGmaster/EndleavesSVGmaster.svg')/svg:svg/svg:defs"
                xpath-default-namespace="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg"
                copy-namespaces="no"/>
            <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Left
endleaves</desc>
            <xsl:call-template name="title">
                <xsl:with-param name="side" select="'left'"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="use" select="'use'"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
            <xsl:variable name="unknown">
                <xsl:choose>
                    <xsl:when test="./yes/type[NC | NK]">
                        <xsl:text>ncNK</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:when>
                    <xsl:when test="./yes/type[other]">
                        <xsl:text>other</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:when>
                </xsl:choose>
            </xsl:variable>
            <xsl:call-template name="description">
                <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
                    select="if (type/separate/units/unit/components/component/type/hook/type/textHook) then $Ay + $delta + 100 + $delta *
count(type/separate/units/unit/components/component[type/hook/type/textHook]) else
$Ay + $delta + 100"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="unknown" select="$unknown"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
            <svg>
                <xsl:attribute name="x">
                    <xsl:value-of select="$0x"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
                <xsl:attribute name="y">
                    <xsl:value-of select="$0y"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
                <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleaves">
                    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="false()"/>
                </xsl:call-template>
            </svg>
        </svg>

```

```

        </xsl:result-document>
        <!-- draw STRUCTURE diagram (i.e. with differentiation between
pastedowns or not -->
        <xsl:result-document href="{filenameLeft_structure}" method="xml"
indent="yes"
        encoding="utf-8" doctype-public="-//W3C//DTD SVG 1.1//EN"
        doctype-system="http://www.w3.org/Graph-
ics/SVG/1.1/DTD/svg11.dtd">
        <xsl:processing-instruction name="xml-stylesheet">
        <xsl:text>href="../../../../GitHub/XSLTransforma-
tions/Endleaves/CSS/style.css"&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:text>type="text/css"</xsl:text>
</xsl:processing-instruction>
        <xsl:text>&#10;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:comment>
        <xsl:text>SVG file generated on: </xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="format-dateTime(current-dateTime(), '[D]
[MNn] [Y] at [H]:[m]:[s]')"/>
        <xsl:text> using </xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="system-property('xsl:product-name')"/>
        <xsl:text> version </xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="system-property('xsl:product-version')"/>
</xsl:comment>
        <xsl:text>&#10;</xsl:text>
        <svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" xmlns:xlink="ht-
tp://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
        version="1.1" x="0" y="0" width="420mm" height="297mm"
viewBox="0 0 420 297"
        preserveAspectRatio="xMidYMid meet">
        <title>Left endleaves of book: <xsl:value-of se-
lect="$shelfmark"/></title>
        <xsl:copy-of
select="document('../SVGmaster/EndleavesSVGmas-
ter.svg')/svg:svg/svg:defs"
        xpath-default-namespace="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg"
copy-namespaces="no"/>
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Left
endleaves</desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="title">
        <xsl:with-param name="side" select="'left'"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="use" select="'structure'"/>
</xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:variable name="unknown">
        <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="./yes/type[NC | NK]">
        <xsl:text>ncNK</xsl:text>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./yes/type[other]">
        <xsl:text>other</xsl:text>
        </xsl:when>
        </xsl:choose>
</xsl:variable>
        <xsl:call-template name="description">
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
select="if (type/separate/units/unit/compon-
ents/component/type/hook/type/textHook) then $Ay + $delta + 100 + $delta *
count(type/separate/units/unit/components/component[type/hook/type/textHook]) else
$Ay + $delta + 100"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="unknown" select="$unknown"/>
</xsl:call-template>
        <svg>
        <xsl:attribute name="x">
        <xsl:value-of select="$0x"/>
</xsl:attribute>

```

```

        <xsl:attribute name="y">
            <xsl:value-of select="$0y"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleaves">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="true()"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </svg>
</xsl:result-document>
</xsl:for-each>
<xsl:for-each select="book/endleaves/right">
    <!-- draw USE diagram (i.e. no differentiation between pastedowns
or not -->
        <xsl:result-document href="{filenameRight_use}" method="xml"
indent="yes"
            encoding="utf-8" doctype-public "-//W3C//DTD SVG 1.1//EN"
            doctype-system="http://www.w3.org/Graph-
ics/SVG/1.1/DTD/svg11.dtd">
            <xsl:processing-instruction name="xml-stylesheet">
                <xsl:text>href="../../../../GitHub/XSLTransforma-
tions/Endleaves/CSS/style.css"&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:text>type="text/css"</xsl:text>
            </xsl:processing-instruction>
            <svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" xmlns:xlink="ht-
tp://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
                version="1.1" x="0" y="0" width="420mm" height="297mm"
                viewBox="0 0 420 297"
                preserveAspectRatio="xMidYMid meet">
                <title>Right endleaves of book: <xsl:value-of se-
lect="$shelfmark"/></title>
                <xsl:copy-of
                    select="document('../SVGmaster/EndleavesSVGmas-
ter.svg')/svg:svg/svg:defs"
                    xpath-default-namespace="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg"
                    copy-namespaces="no"/>
                <xsl:call-template name="title">
                    <xsl:with-param name="side" select="'right'"/>
                    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="'use'"/>
                </xsl:call-template>
                <xsl:variable name="unknown">
                    <xsl:choose>
                        <xsl:when test="./yes/type[NC | NK]">
                            <xsl:text>nCNK</xsl:text>
                        </xsl:when>
                        <xsl:when test="./yes/type[other]">
                            <xsl:text>other</xsl:text>
                        </xsl:when>
                    </xsl:choose>
                </xsl:variable>
                <xsl:call-template name="description">
                    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
                        select="if (type/separate/units/unit/compon-
ents/component/type/hook/type/textHook) then $Ay + $delta + 100 + $delta *
count(type/separate/units/unit/components/component[type/hook/type/textHook]) else
$Ay + $delta + 100"/>
                    <xsl:with-param name="unknown" select="$unknown"/>
                </xsl:call-template>
                <g transform="scale(-1 1)">
                    <desc>Right endleaves</desc>
                <svg>
                    <xsl:attribute name="x">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$0x - 365"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                    <xsl:attribute name="y">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$0y"/>

```

```

        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleaves">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="false()"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </svg>
</g>
</svg>
</xsl:result-document>
<!-- draw STRUCTURE diagram (i.e. with differentiation between
pastedowns or not -->
<xsl:result-document href="{filenameRight_structure}" meth-
od="xml" indent="yes"
encoding="utf-8" doctype-public="//W3C//DTD SVG 1.1//EN"
doctype-system="http://www.w3.org/Graph-
ics/SVG/1.1/DTD/svg11.dtd">
    <xsl:processing-instruction name="xml-stylesheet">
        <xsl:text>href="../../../../GitHub/XSLTransforma-
tions/Endleaves/CSS/style.css"&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:text>type="text/css"</xsl:text>
    </xsl:processing-instruction>
    <svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" xmlns:xlink="ht-
tp://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
version="1.1" x="0" y="0" width="420mm" height="297mm"
viewBox="0 0 420 297"
preserveAspectRatio="xMidYMid meet">
        <title>Right endleaves of book: <xsl:value-of se-
lect="$shelfmark"/></title>
        <xsl:copy-of
select="document('../SVGmaster/EndleavesSVGmas-
ter.svg')/svg:svg/svg:defs"
xpath-default-namespace="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg"
copy-namespaces="no"/>
        <xsl:call-template name="title">
            <xsl:with-param name="side" select="'right'"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="'structure'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:variable name="unknown">
            <xsl:choose>
                <xsl:when test="./yes/type[NC | NK]">
                    <xsl:text>ncNK</xsl:text>
                </xsl:when>
                <xsl:when test="./yes/type[other]">
                    <xsl:text>other</xsl:text>
                </xsl:when>
            </xsl:choose>
        </xsl:variable>
        <xsl:call-template name="description">
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
select="if (type/separate/units/unit/compon-
ents/component/type/hook/type/textHook) then $Ay + $delta + 100 + $delta *
count(type/separate/units/unit/components/component[type/hook/type/textHook]) else
$Ay + $delta + 100"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="unknown" select="$unknown"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <g transform="scale(-1 1)">
            <desc>Right endleaves</desc>
            <svg>
                <xsl:attribute name="x">
                    <xsl:value-of select="$0x - 365"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
                <xsl:attribute name="y">
                    <xsl:value-of select="$0y"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
                <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleaves">

```

```

        <xsl:with-param name="use" select="true()"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </svg>
</g>
</svg>
</xsl:result-document>
</xsl:for-each>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="title">
            <xsl:with-param name="detected" select="0"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </svg>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleaves">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()"/>
    <xsl:choose>
        <!-- If endleaves are present, then the right sequence of templates is
called to construct the diagram, otherwise only the outer gathering is drawn -->
        <xsl:when test="self::node()[yes | no]">
            <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                <xsl:choose>
                    <xsl:when test="./yes/type/separate/units/unit//hook/type[text-
Hook]">
                        <!-- shorter outermost gathering -->
                        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                            <xsl:choose>
                                <xsl:when test="./yes/type[integral]">
                                    <xsl:attribute name="class">
                                        <xsl:text>line</xsl:text>
                                    </xsl:attribute>
                                </xsl:when>
                                <xsl:otherwise>
                                    <xsl:attribute name="class">
                                        <xsl:text>line_ref</xsl:text>
                                    </xsl:attribute>
                                </xsl:otherwise>
                            </xsl:choose>
                            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
                                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="$Ay"/>
                                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
                                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="$Ay"/>
                                <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="10"/>
                                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="10"/>
                                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:text>0</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:text>0</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:text>0</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
                                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="$Ay + 20"/>

```

```

        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ay + 20"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;z</xsl:text>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <use xlink:href="#outermostGL">
        <xsl:choose>
            <xsl:when test="./yes/type[integral]">
                <xsl:attribute name="class">
                    <xsl:text>line</xsl:text>
                </xsl:attribute>
            </xsl:when>
            <xsl:otherwise>
                <xsl:attribute name="class">
                    <xsl:text>line_ref</xsl:text>
                </xsl:attribute>
            </xsl:otherwise>
        </xsl:choose>
        <xsl:attribute name="x">
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:attribute name="y">
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ay"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </use>
    <use xlink:href="#outermostGL">
        <xsl:attribute name="class">
            <xsl:text>line_ref</xsl:text>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:attribute name="x">
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:attribute name="y">
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ay + $delta + 20"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </use>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</g>
<xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="./yes/type[integral]">
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
</xsl:choose>
<xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="./yes/type[separate]">
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparate">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type of endleaves
not checked, not
        known, or other</desc>
    </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:when>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

```

```

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesIntegral">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
  <xsl:param name="totLeaves" select="./yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves"
as="xs:integer"/>
  <xsl:param name="currentLeaf" select="1"/>
  <xsl:variable name="baseline_int" select="$Ay"/>
  <xsl:variable name="B1x" select="$Ax - 145"/>
  <xsl:variable name="B1y"
    select="$baseline_int - ($delta * $totLeaves) - ($delta * ($totLeaves
- $currentLeaf)) - 5 -
    (if (./yes/type/separate//pastedown/yes) then ($delta *
(count(./yes/type/separate//pastedown/yes)) else 0)"/>
  <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Integral endleaves</desc>
  <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Leaf N.<xsl:value-of
    select="$totLeaves - $currentLeaf + 1"/></desc>
  <xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="./yes/type/integral/pastedown[yes] and $use eq false()">

      <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Pastedown">
        <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:in-
teger"/>

        <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline_int" select="$baseline_int"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
      </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="./yes/type/integral/pastedown[yes] and $use eq true()">

      <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaves">
        <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:in-
teger"/>

        <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline_int" select="$baseline_int"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
      </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="./yes/type/integral/pastedown[no]">
      <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaves">
        <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:in-
teger"/>

        <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline_int" select="$baseline_int"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
      </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
      <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Integral flyleaves not
checked, not known,
      or other.</desc>
      <!-- Draw as if no, but with uncertainty -->
      <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaves">
        <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:in-
teger"/>

        <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline_int" select="$baseline_int"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="if ($use eq true())
then 100 else 50"/>

```

```

        <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Pastedown">
    <xsl:param name="totLeaves" as="xs:integer"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentLeaf"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline_int"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1x"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1y"/>
    <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="$currentLeaf = $totLeaves">
            <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Pastedown</desc>
            <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                <use xlink:href="#pastedown">
                    <xsl:attribute name="x">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$B1x"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                    <xsl:attribute name="y">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                </use>
                <path>
                    <xsl:attribute name="class">
                        <xsl:text>line</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                    <xsl:attribute name="d">
                        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
                        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline_int + 10"/>
                        <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
                        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
                        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
                        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                </path>
            </g>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="$currentLeaf lt $totLeaves">
            <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Flyleaf</desc>
            <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaf">
                <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:in-
teger"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="baseline_int" select="$baseline_int"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
            <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral">
                <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:in-
teger"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf + 1"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaves">

```

```

<xsl:param name="use" select="false()"/>
<xsl:param name="totLeaves" as="xs:integer"/>
<xsl:param name="currentLeaf"/>
<xsl:param name="baseline_int"/>
<xsl:param name="B1x"/>
<xsl:param name="B1y"/>
<xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
<xsl:choose>
  <xsl:when test="$currentLeaf = $totLeaves">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Flyleaf</desc>
    <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaf">
      <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:integer"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="baseline_int" select="$baseline_int"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
  </xsl:when>
  <xsl:when test="$currentLeaf lt $totLeaves">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Flyleaf</desc>
    <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaf">
      <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:integer"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="baseline_int" select="$baseline_int"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesIntegral">
      <xsl:with-param name="totLeaves" select="$totLeaves" as="xs:integer"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="currentLeaf" select="$currentLeaf + 1"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
  </xsl:when>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesIntegral-Flyleaf">
  <xsl:param name="totLeaves"/>
  <xsl:param name="currentLeaf"/>
  <xsl:param name="baseline_int"/>
  <xsl:param name="B1x"/>
  <xsl:param name="B1y"/>
  <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100" as="xs:integer"/>
  <xsl:variable name="Ax"
    select="if (./yes/type/separate/units/unit/components/component/type/hook/type/textHook) then $Ax + 6 else $Ax"/>
  <xsl:variable name="Ax2"
    select="if (./yes/type/separate/units/unit/components/component/type/hook/type/textHook) then $Ax + 134 else $Ax + 140"/>
  <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <path>
      <xsl:attribute name="class">
        <xsl:text>line</xsl:text>
      </xsl:attribute>
      <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'2'"/>
      </xsl:call-template>
      <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
  </g>

```

```

        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline_int + 10"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="($baseline_int - ($delta * $currentLeaf))"/>

        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 10"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="($baseline_int - ($delta * $currentLeaf))"/>

        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax2"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="($baseline_int - ($delta * $currentLeaf))"/>

    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</g>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparate">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Separate endleaves</desc>
    <xsl:for-each select="./yes/type/separate/units/unit">
        <!-- Variable to count the number of Units -->
        <xsl:variable name="countUnits" select="last()"/>
        <!-- Counter variable for the current unit -->
        <xsl:variable name="currentUnit" select="position()"/>
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Unit N. <xsl:value-of select="$currentUnit"
        /></desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparate_components">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="countUnits" select="$countUnits"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="currentUnit" select="$currentUnit"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
                select="if (following-sibling::unit[1]/components/component//type[textHook]) then $Ay - $delta * count(following-sibling::unit[1]/components/component)
                    - (if (ancestor::yes/type/integral) then $delta * count(ancestor::yes/type/integral/xs:integer(numberOfLeaves)) + $delta * 1.5 else 0)
                    else $Ay - ((if (ancestor::yes/type[integral]) then $delta * ancestor::yes/type/integral/xs:integer(numberOfLeaves) else 0)
                        + (if (preceding-sibling::unit[1]/components/component//type[textHook]) then $delta * count(preceding-sibling::unit[1]/components/component) else 0)
                        + (if (components/component//type[textHook]) then (if (ancestor::yes/type/integral) then - $delta * ancestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves else 0)
                            else $delta * 2 * count(following-sibling::unit/components/component)
                            + (($delta - 2) * count(following-sibling::unit[not(components//type[textHook]]))))
                        - (if (following-sibling::unit[1]/components/component/type[singleLeaf | NC | NK | other]) then $delta * 1.5 else 0)
                    ))"
                />
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:for-each>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparate_components">

```

```

<xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
<xsl:param name="countUnits"/>
<xsl:param name="currentUnit"/>
<xsl:param name="baseline"/>
<xsl:for-each select="./components/component">
  <!-- Variable to count the number of Components -->
  <xsl:variable name="countComponents" select="last()"/>
  <!-- Counter variable for the current component -->
  <xsl:variable name="currentComponent" select="position()"/>
  <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:attribute name="class">
      <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="material/parchment">
          <xsl:text>line2</xsl:text>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:otherwise>
          <xsl:text>line</xsl:text>
        </xsl:otherwise>
      </xsl:choose>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Component N. <xsl:value-of
      select="$currentComponent"/></desc>
    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[textHook]">
        <use xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" xlink:href="#outer-
mostGL">
          <xsl:attribute name="class">
            <xsl:text>line_ref</xsl:text>
          </xsl:attribute>
          <xsl:attribute name="x">
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
          </xsl:attribute>
          <xsl:attribute name="y">
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ay + $delta + 20 + $delta *
$countComponents"
          />
          </xsl:attribute>
        </use>
      </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="./pastedown[yes] and $use eq false()">
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Pastedown</desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown">
          <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
          <xsl:with-param name="countComponents"/>
          <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$current-
Component"/>
          <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
      </xsl:when>
      <xsl:when test="./pastedown[yes] and $use eq true()">
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Flyleaves</desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves">
          <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
          <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
          <xsl:with-param name="countComponents"/>
          <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$current-
Component"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
      </xsl:when>
      <xsl:when test="./pastedown[no]">

```

```

        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Flyleaves</desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$count-
Components"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$current-
Component"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type of endleaf
component not
        checked, not known, or other</desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$count-
Components"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$current-
Component"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty"
                select="if ($use eq true()) then 100 else 50"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</g>
</xsl:for-each>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100" as="xs:integer"/>
    <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="./type[fold]">
            <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type fold</desc>
            <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-Fold">
                <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentCompon-
ent"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./type[guard]">
            <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type guard</desc>
            <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-Guard">
                <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentCompon-
ent"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./type[hook]">
            <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type hook</desc>
            <xsl:choose>
                <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[endleafHook]">

```

```

hook</desc>
EndleafHook">
Components"/>
Component"/>
TextHook">
Components"/>
Component"/>
not known, or
other type</desc>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:when test="./type[outsideHook]">
<desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type outside hook</desc>
<xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-OutsideHook">
<xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
<xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
<xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
<xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentComponent"/>
<xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:when test="./type[singleLeaf]">
<desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type single leaf</desc>
<xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaf-SingleLeaf">
<xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
<xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
<xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
<xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentComponent"/>
<xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty" as="xs:integer"/>
</xsl:call-template>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
<xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
<xsl:with-param name="baseline"
select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta *
$currentComponent) + ($delta) else $baseline"/>
<xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>

```

```

        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type not checked, not known,
or other
        type</desc>
        <!-- draw single leaf that fades away at the fold-->
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaf-SingleLeaf">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>

            <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentComponent"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty" as="xs:integer"/>

            <xsl:with-param name="unknown" select="'yes'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="50" as="xs:integer"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
                select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta *
                $currentComponent) + ($delta) else $baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>

        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-Fold">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100" as="xs:integer"/>
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Folded flyleaves</desc>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <path>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

                <xsl:text>#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

                <xsl:text>#32;A</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>

                <xsl:text>#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </g>
</xsl:template>

```

```

        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 - ($delta -
1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
<path>
    <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="$certainty lt 100">
            <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'2'"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - (2 *
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - (2 *
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 - ($delta -
1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
        select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
    />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

```

```

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
  <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
  <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
  <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
  <xsl:variable name="B1x"
    select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) + $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-
sibling::component) * $delta) - 145"/>
  <xsl:variable name="B1y"
    select="$baseline -
    (2 * $delta * $countComponents) -
    (3 * $delta * count(ancestor::unit/preceding-sibling::unit/components/com-
ponent[pastedown/yes])) -
    ($delta * count(preceding-sibling::component)) +
    (if (ancestor::yes/type/integral/pastedown/yes) then ($delta * (ancest-
or::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) + $delta) else 0)
    - 10 +
    (if (./type/hook/type[textHook]) then $delta * $countComponents -
    (if (ancestor::yes/type/integral) then $delta + $delta * ancest-
or::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves else 0) - 5 else 0)"/>
  <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-pastedown">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="unknown"
      select="if (./type[NC | NK | other]) then 'yes' else 'no'"/>
  </xsl:call-template>
<xsl:choose>
  <xsl:when test="./type[fold]">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type fold</desc>
    <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-Fold">
      <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>

      <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentCompon-
ent"/>

      <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
  </xsl:when>
  <xsl:when test="./type[guard]">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type guard</desc>
    <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-Guard">
      <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>

      <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentCompon-
ent"/>

      <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
  </xsl:when>
  <xsl:when test="./type[hook]">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type hook</desc>
    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[endleafHook]">
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type pastedown-
endleaf-hook</desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-
EndleafHook">
          <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>

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```

        <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1yParam" select="$B1y"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$count-
Components"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$current-
Component"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[textHook]">
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type pastedown-
text-hook</desc>
        <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-
TextHook">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$count-
Components"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$current-
Component"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
        <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type not checked,
not known, or
            other type</desc>
    </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:when test="./type[outsideHook]">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type outside hook</desc>
    <xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-OutsideHook">
        <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1x" select="$B1x"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="B1y" select="$B1y"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentCompon-
ent"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:when test="./type[singleLeaf]">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type single leaf</desc>
    <!-- Pastedown already drawn when detected its presence -->
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Type not checked, not known,
or other
        type</desc>
    <!-- Pastedown already drawn when detected its presence -->
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaf-SingleLeaf">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100" as="xs:integer"/>

```

```

<xsl:param name="unknown" select="'no'"/>
<xsl:variable name="Dx" select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
<xsl:variable name="Dy" select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <desc>Parametric path for the flyleaf</desc>
  <path>
    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="$unknown eq 'yes'">
        <xsl:attribute name="stroke">
          <xsl:text>url(#fading)</xsl:text>
        </xsl:attribute>
      </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
      <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Dy"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 2"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Dy + (if ($unknown eq 'yes') then 0.0001
else 0)"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </path>
</g>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaf-SingleLeaf_part">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
  <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
  <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
  <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
  <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100" as="xs:integer"/>
  <xsl:variable name="Dx" select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
  <xsl:variable name="Dy" select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

  <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <desc>Parametric path for the flyleaf</desc>
    <path>
      <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
      </xsl:call-template>
      <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Dy"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Dx"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Dy"/>
      </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
  </g>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-pastedown">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>

```

```

<xsl:param name="B1x"/>
<xsl:param name="B1y"/>
<xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
<xsl:param name="baseline"/>
<xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
<xsl:param name="unknown" select="'no'"/>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" id="{concat('pastedown', position())}">

  <desc>pastedown</desc>
  <path>
    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="$unknown eq 'yes'">
        <xsl:attribute name="stroke">
          <xsl:text>url(#fading2)</xsl:text>
        </xsl:attribute>
      </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
      <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="./type[outsideHook]">
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 115"/>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./type[guard]">
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 95"/>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:otherwise>
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1x"/>
        </xsl:otherwise>
      </xsl:choose>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[textHook]">
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[endleafHook]">
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1y - 5"/>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:otherwise>
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
        </xsl:otherwise>
      </xsl:choose>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[textHook]">
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$B1y + $delta + (if ($unknown eq 'yes') then
0.001 else 0)"
          />
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[endleafHook]">
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$B1y - 5 + (if ($unknown eq 'yes') then
0.001 else 0)"/>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:otherwise>
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + (if ($unknown eq 'yes')
then 0.001 else 0)"
          />
      </xsl:choose>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </path>

```

```

        </xsl:otherwise>
    </xsl:choose>
</xsl:attribute>
</path>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <use xlink:href="#pasted">
        <xsl:attribute name="x">
            <xsl:value-of select="$B1x"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:choose>
            <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[textHook]">
                <xsl:attribute name="y">
                    <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
            </xsl:when>
            <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[endleafHook]">
                <xsl:attribute name="y">
                    <xsl:value-of select="$B1y - 5"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
            </xsl:when>
            <xsl:otherwise>
                <xsl:attribute name="y">
                    <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
            </xsl:otherwise>
        </xsl:choose>
    </xsl:choose>
    <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="./type[guard]">
            <xsl:attribute name="clip-path">
                <xsl:text>url(#guardClip)</xsl:text>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./type[outsideHook]">
            <xsl:attribute name="clip-path">
                <xsl:text>url(#outsideHookClip)</xsl:text>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
    </use>
</g>
</g>
<xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="./type[singleLeaf]">
        <!-- do not call the component attachment -->
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
        <xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
            <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>

            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty"
                select="if ($unknown eq 'yes') then 50 else 100" as="xs:in-
teger"/>

            <xsl:with-param name="onlySewn"
                select="if (./type[singleLeaf]) then 'yes' else 'no'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-Fold">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1x"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1y"/>

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```

<xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
<xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
<xsl:param name="baseline"/>
<xsl:variable name="Dx" select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
<xsl:variable name="Dy" select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

<xsl:call-template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaf-SingleLeaf_part">
  <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
  <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
  <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
  <xsl:with-param name="currentComponent" select="$currentComponent"/>
</xsl:call-template>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <desc>Parametric path describing the fold from the flyleaf to the
pastedown</desc>
  <path>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Dx"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Dy"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
        select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
        select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component))"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component))"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </path>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
  <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
  <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
  <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
    select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
  />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-Guard">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>

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```

<xsl:param name="baseline"/>
<xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
<xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
<desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Flyleaf guard</desc>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <path>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $countCompon-
ents)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 - ($delta -
1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </path>
  <path>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $countCom-
ponents)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - (2 *
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - (2 *
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>

```

```

        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 - ($delta -
1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
        select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
    />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-Guard">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1x"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1y"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:variable name="Dx" select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
    <xsl:variable name="Dy" select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <desc>Parametric path describing the fold from the flyleaf to the
pastedown</desc>
        <path>
            <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                <xsl:with-param name="certainty"
                    select="if ($currentComponent eq $countComponents) then 50
else 100"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $countCompon-
ents)"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>

```

```

        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component))"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</g>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <desc>Parametric path describing the fold from the flyleaf to the
pastedown</desc>
    <path>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component))"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component))"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
        select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
    />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-EndleafHook">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Endleaf-hook</desc>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:choose>
            <xsl:when test="./type/hook/double/yes">
                <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                        <xsl:attribute name="d">
                            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>

```

```

        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
Component) + 2"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countCompon-
ents)"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
Component) + 2"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) + 2.5"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) + 2.5"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2
- ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)) - 2"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $count-
Components) - 5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
<path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>

        <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent))
- (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))) - 2"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countCompon-
ents)"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent))
- (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))) - 2"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) + 2.5"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) + 2.5"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>

```

```

        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2
- ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)) - 2"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $count-
Components) - 5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</g>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $countCom-
ponents)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent) - 1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countCom-
ponents)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent) - 1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 0.5"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 0.5"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
- 2 - ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)) + 1"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline - ($delta * $countCompon-
ents) - 5"/>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
            <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of

```

```

                    select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)) - (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))) +
1"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countCom-
ponents)"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                    select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)) - (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))) +
1"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 0.5"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 0.5"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
- 2 - ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)) + 1"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline - ($delta * $countCompon-
ents) - 5"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                </path>
            </g>
            <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" stroke-line-
cap="round">
                <!-- always uncertain as the schema does not tell if
the double is a single or two sheets -->
                <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                    <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="50"/>
                    <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
                </xsl:call-template>
                <xsl:attribute name="d">
                    <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) - 1"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $countComponents)
+ 2"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) - 1"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $countComponents)
+ 2"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component)"/>

```

```

                <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $countComponents)
+ 2"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + 2"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + 2"
                />
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </g>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
- 2"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta)"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta)"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 -
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countCom-
ponents) - 5"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>

```

```

                <xsl:value-of
                    select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent))
- (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)))"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
- 2"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent))
- (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)))"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com
ponent) * $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com
ponent) * $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 -
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countCom
ponents) - 5"/>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
        select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
    />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-EndleafHook">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1x"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1yParam"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
    <xsl:variable name="Dx" select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
    <xsl:variable name="Dy" select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

    <xsl:variable name="B1y" select="$B1yParam - 5"/>
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Pastedown endleaf-hook</desc>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:choose>
            <xsl:when test="./type/hook/double/yes">
                <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                    <xsl:attribute name="d">
                        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>

```

```

Components)"/>
    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
    <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
    - 2"/>
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
    <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
    select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
    <xsl:text>&#32;,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
    select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countCom-
    <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
    select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
    <xsl:text>&#32;,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
<path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
    <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
    - 2"/>
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
    <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
    <xsl:text>&#32;,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="0"/>

```

```

        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
- 2"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent))
- (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)))/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent))
- (2 * ($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)))/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="50"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
Components) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
Components) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
Components) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent) + 2"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent) + 2"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>

```

```

        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
          <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents)
- 2"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentCom-
ponent)"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta)"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta)"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component))"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countCom-
ponents) - 5"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component))"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
      </path>
    </xsl:otherwise>
  </xsl:choose>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
  <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
  <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
  <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
    select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
  />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-TextHook">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
  <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
  <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>

```

```

<xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
<xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
<desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Text-hook</desc>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="./type/hook/double/yes">
      <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
          <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) +
$delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
          </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
      </g>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="ancestor::yes/type/integral">
      <path>
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
          <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"/>
          <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
          <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
          <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
          <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - $delta * (count(following-
sibling::component))"/>
          <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>

```

```

        <xsl:value-of
            select="($baseline - ($delta * ancestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sibling::component))"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 16"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="($baseline - ($delta * ancestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sibling::component))"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="($baseline - ($delta * ancestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sibling::component))"
        />
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta * $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta * $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) + $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</xsl:otherwise>

```

```

        </xsl:choose>
    </g>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
            <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                <xsl:attribute name="d">
                    <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                        select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                        select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta
* $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                        select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta
* $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                        select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) + 0.5"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                        select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) + 0.5"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
                    <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of
                        select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 1"/>
                    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
            </path>
            <xsl:choose>
                <xsl:when test="ancestor::yes/type/integral">
                    <path>
                        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" se-
lect="$certainty"/>
                            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
                        </xsl:call-template>
                        <xsl:attribute name="d">
                            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                            <xsl:value-of
                                select="$Ax - ($delta * $countCom-
ponents) + $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 1"/>
                            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
                            <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
                            <xsl:value-of
                                select="$Ax - $delta * (count(fol-
lowing-sibling::component)) - 2"/>
                            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                            <xsl:value-of

```

```

        select="($baseline - ($delta * an-
cestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - 2 - $delta * (count(following-
sibling::component))"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 16"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
        select="($baseline - ($delta * an-
cestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - 2 - $delta * (count(following-
sibling::component))"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
        select="($baseline - ($delta * an-
cestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - 2 - $delta * (count(following-
sibling::component))"
        />
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" se-
lect="$certainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta
* $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - 1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta +
10"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta
* $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - 1"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta + 10 + (count(follow-
ing-sibling::component) * $delta) + 0.5"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta + 10 + (count(follow-
ing-sibling::component) * $delta) + 0.5"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - ($delta * $countCom-
ponents) + $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 1"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
        </xsl:attribute>

```

```

        </path>
    </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</g>
<path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="50"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'3'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $count-
Components) + 2"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $count-
Components) + 2"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $count-
Components) + 2"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"
        />
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</g>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $count-
Components)"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of

```

```

                select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) +
$delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
        <xsl:choose>
            <xsl:when test="ancestor::yes/type/integral">
                <path>
                    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"/>
                        <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
                    </xsl:call-template>
                    <xsl:attribute name="d">
                        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of
                        select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
                        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
                        <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of
                        select="$Ax - $delta * (count(following-
sibling::component))"/>
                        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of
                        select="($baseline - ($delta * ancest-
or::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sib-
ling::component))"/>
                        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 16"/>
                        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of
                        select="($baseline - ($delta * ancest-
or::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sib-
ling::component))"/>
                        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
                        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of

```

```

                select="($baseline - ($delta * ancestor::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sibling::component))"
            />
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta
* $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta
* $countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>A</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-
sibling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-
sibling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</g>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <!-- GOOD -->
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
        select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline + ($delta * $countCom-
ponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) else $baseline"
    />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

```

```

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-TextHook">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
  <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
  <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
  <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
  <xsl:param name="B1x"/>
  <xsl:param name="B1y"/>
  <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
  <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Text-hook</desc>
  <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="./type/hook/double/yes">
        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
          <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
          </xsl:call-template>
          <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
            <xsl:text>A</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) + 0.5"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) + 0.5"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
            <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
              select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) + $delta
- 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 2"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
          </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
      </xsl:when>
      <xsl:when test="ancestor::yes/type/integral">
        <path>
          <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
          </xsl:call-template>
          <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of

```

```

        select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 2"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 2"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 2"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) - 2"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
<path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
        <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
        <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>

```

```

        <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) + $delta
- 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
        <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
<xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="ancestor::yes/type/integral">
        <path>
            <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax - $delta * (count(following-
sibling::component))"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="($baseline - ($delta * ancest-
or::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sib-
ling::component))"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 16"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="($baseline - ($delta * ancest-
or::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sib-
ling::component))"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="($baseline - ($delta * ancest-
or::yes/type/integral/numberOfLeaves) - $delta) - $delta * (count(following-sib-
ling::component))"
                    />
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">

```

```

tainty"/>
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
      <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
        select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) + 1"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
        select="$baseline - ($delta + ($delta *
$countComponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent)) + 1"/>
      <xsl:text>A</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
        select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
        select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sib-
ling::component) * $delta) - 1.5"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
        select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents)
+ $delta - 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta) + 1"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </path>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
<path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
    <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="50"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
  </xsl:call-template>
  <xsl:attribute name="d">
    <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
      select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
    <xsl:text>Q</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
      select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $countCompon-
ents) + 2"/>
    <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of
      select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) + 1"/>
    <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
    <xsl:value-of

```

```

                select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $countCompon-
ents) + 2"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $countCompon-
ents) + 2"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent) - 1"
                />
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
        <path xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
            <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
                <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
                <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
            </xsl:call-template>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta *
$countComponents)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$baseline + $delta + 20 + ($delta * $count-
Components) - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta + 10 + (count(following-sibling::com-
ponent) * $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) + $delta
- 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>

```

```

        <xsl:text>&#32;Q</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of
            select="$Ax - ($delta * $countComponents) + $delta
- 1 + (count(preceding-sibling::component) * $delta)"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
        <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
        <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y + $delta"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
</path>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
        select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline + ($delta * $countCom-
ponents) - ($delta * $currentComponent) else $baseline"
    />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparateFlyleaves-OutsideHook">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="certainty"/>
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Outside hook</desc>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <path>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of
                    select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 - ($delta -
1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)"/>
                <xsl:text></xsl:text>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </g>
</xsl:template>

```

```

        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
    <path>
        <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
        </xsl:call-template>
        <xsl:attribute name="d">
            <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + (2 * $delta) + ($delta * $countCom-
ponents)"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - (2 *
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)))/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="($baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)) - (2 *
($delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta)))/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;A</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
            <xsl:text>&#32;</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2 - ($delta -
1 + (count(following-sibling::component) * $delta))"/>
            <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
</g>
<xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
        select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
    />
</xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="leftEndleavesSeparatePastedown-OutsideHook">
    <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1x"/>
    <xsl:param name="B1y"/>
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="currentComponent"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:variable name="Dx" select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>

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```

<xsl:variable name="Dy" select="$baseline - ($delta * $currentComponent)"/>

<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <desc>Parametric path for the flyleaf</desc>
  <path>
    <!-- Because the schema does not go down to the element level and
does not allow for each part of the endleaf
    to be pasted as pastedown, this flyleaf id drawn as uncertain
to accommodate for the possibility that it
    was actually a pastedown as it is common in Dutch bindings -->
    <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
      <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="50"/>
      <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
    </xsl:call-template>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 140"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Dy"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Dx"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Dy"/>
      <xsl:text>A</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of
select="$delta - 1 + (count(following-sibling::component)
* $delta)"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="0"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="1"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </path>
</g>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <desc>Parametric path describing the fold from the flyleaf to the
pastedown</desc>
  <path>
    <xsl:attribute name="d">
      <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - 2 + ($delta * count(preceding-sib-
ling::component)"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
      <xsl:text>L</xsl:text>
      <xsl:value-of select="$B1x + 130"/>
      <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>

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```

        <xsl:value-of select="$B1y"/>
      </xsl:attribute>
    </path>
  </g>
  <xsl:call-template name="componentAttachment">
    <xsl:with-param name="use" select="$use"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$countComponents"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="baseline"
      select="if (attachment/glued) then $baseline - ($delta * $current-
Component) + ($delta) else $baseline"
    />
  </xsl:call-template>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="componentAttachment">
  <xsl:param name="use" select="false()" as="xs:boolean"/>
  <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
  <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
  <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
  <xsl:param name="onlySewn" select="'no'"/>
  <!-- Only draw the sewn attachment and not the glued option for single leaves
and all units but textHook if there is a integral pastedown -->
  <xsl:variable name="onlySewn"
    select="if (($onlySewn eq 'yes') or
      (ancestor::yes/type/integral/pastedown/yes and
boolean(not(type/hook/type[textHook])))
    ) then 'yes' else 'no'"/>
  <xsl:variable name="rotation"
    select="if (boolean(
      (pastedown/yes and $use eq false() and $countComponents le 3)
      or (following-sibling::component/pastedown/yes and $use eq false() and
$countComponents le 3)
      or (preceding-sibling::component/pastedown/yes and $use eq false() and
$countComponents le 3)
    )) then 45 else 0"/>
  <xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="./attachment[sewn]">
      <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Sewn component</desc>
      <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[textHook]">
          <xsl:call-template name="sewnComponent-textHook">
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$count-
Components"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
          </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[endleafHook]">
          <xsl:call-template name="sewnComponent-endleafHook">
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$count-
Components"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="rotation" select="$rotation"/>
          </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:otherwise>
          <xsl:call-template name="sewnComponent">
            <xsl:with-param name="countComponents" select="$count-
Components"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="rotation" select="$rotation"/>
          </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:otherwise>
      </xsl:choose>
    </xsl:when>
  </xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

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```

<xsl:when test="./attachment[glued]">
  <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Glued component</desc>
  <xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="./type/hook/type[textHook]">
      <xsl:call-template name="gluedComponent-textHook">
        <xsl:with-param name="baseline" select="$baseline"/>
      </xsl:call-template>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:otherwise>
      <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="$onlySewn eq 'no'">
          <!-- Only draw the sewn attachment and not the glued
option for single leaves and all units but textHook if there is a integral pastedown
-->
          <xsl:call-template name="gluedComponent">
            <xsl:with-param name="baseline" se-
lect="$baseline"/>
            <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$cer-
tainty"
as="xs:integer"/>
          </xsl:call-template>
        </xsl:when>
      </xsl:choose>
    </xsl:otherwise>
  </xsl:choose>
  <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">Attachment method not
checked, not known,
or other</desc>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="sewnComponent">
  <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
  <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
  <xsl:param name="rotation" select="0"/>
  <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <path>
      <xsl:attribute name="class">
        <xsl:text>thread</xsl:text>
      </xsl:attribute>
      <xsl:attribute name="transform">
        <xsl:text>rotate(</xsl:text>
<xsl:value-of select="- $rotation"/>
<xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
<xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
<xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
<xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
<xsl:text>)</xsl:text>
      </xsl:attribute>
      <xsl:attribute name="d">
        <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
<xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
<xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
<xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
<xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
<xsl:value-of select="$Ax - ($delta * 1.5)"/>
<xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
<xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
      </xsl:attribute>

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```

        </path>
    </g>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="sewnComponent-endleafHook">
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="rotation" select="0"/>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <path>
            <xsl:attribute name="class">
                <xsl:text>thread</xsl:text>
            </xsl:attribute>
            <xsl:attribute name="transform">
                <xsl:text>rotate(</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="-$rotation"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
                <xsl:text>)</xsl:text>
            </xsl:attribute>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta * $countComponents) - 2"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - ($delta * 1.2)"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - ($delta * $countComponents)
- 5"/>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </g>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="sewnComponent-textHook">
    <xsl:param name="countComponents"/>
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <path>
            <xsl:attribute name="class">
                <xsl:text>thread</xsl:text>
            </xsl:attribute>
            <xsl:attribute name="d">
                <xsl:text>M</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + $delta + 10 - 3"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
                <xsl:text>&#32;L</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$Ax - ($delta * 2)"/>
                <xsl:text>,</xsl:text>
                <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 10"/>
            </xsl:attribute>
        </path>
    </g>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="gluedComponent">
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100"/>
    <xsl:variable name="componentID" select="generate-id()"/>

```

```

<mask xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <xsl:attribute name="id">
    <xsl:value-of select="concat('fademask', $componentID)"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <rect>
    <xsl:attribute name="width">
      <xsl:value-of select="$delta * 2.5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="height">
      <xsl:value-of select="$delta"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="x">
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta div 2)"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="y">
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - $delta "/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="fill">
      <xsl:text>url(#radialFading)</xsl:text>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="stroke-opacity">
      <xsl:value-of select="0.0"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </rect>
</mask>
<g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <xsl:call-template name="certainty">
    <xsl:with-param name="certainty" select="$certainty"/>
    <xsl:with-param name="type" select="'4'"/>
  </xsl:call-template>
  <rect>
    <xsl:attribute name="width">
      <xsl:value-of select="$delta * 2.5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="height">
      <xsl:value-of select="$delta"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="x">
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + ($delta div 2)"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="y">
      <xsl:value-of select="$baseline - $delta "/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="fill">
      <xsl:text>url(#gluedPattern2)</xsl:text>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="stroke-opacity">
      <xsl:value-of select="0.0"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="mask">
      <xsl:value-of select="concat('url(#fademask', $componentID,
'))"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
  </rect>
</g>
</xsl:template>

<xsl:template name="gluedComponent-textHook">
  <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
  <xsl:variable name="componentID" select="generate-id()"/>
  <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <desc xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
      <xsl:text>Glued component - textHook</xsl:text>
    </desc>
    <mask xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">

```

```

<xsl:attribute name="id">
  <xsl:value-of select="concat('fademask', $componentID)"/>
</xsl:attribute>
<rect xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <xsl:attribute name="width">
    <xsl:value-of select="$delta * 2.5"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="height">
    <xsl:value-of select="$delta"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="x">
    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 1.5*($delta)"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="y">
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 20 "/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="fill">
    <xsl:text>url(#radialFading)</xsl:text>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="stroke-opacity">
    <xsl:value-of select="0.0"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
</rect>
</mask>
<rect xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
  <xsl:attribute name="width">
    <xsl:value-of select="$delta * 2.5"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="height">
    <xsl:value-of select="$delta"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="x">
    <xsl:value-of select="$Ax + 1.5*($delta)"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="y">
    <xsl:value-of select="$baseline + 20 "/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="fill">
    <xsl:text>url(#gluedPattern2)</xsl:text>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="stroke-opacity">
    <xsl:value-of select="0.0"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
  <xsl:attribute name="mask">
    <xsl:value-of select="concat('url(#fademask', $componentID,
'))"/>
  </xsl:attribute>
</rect>
</g>
</xsl:template>

<!-- Titling -->
<xsl:template name="title">
  <xsl:param name="detected" as="xs:integer" select="1"/>
  <xsl:param name="side" select="'left'"/>
  <xsl:param name="use" select="'use'"/>
  <text xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:attribute name="class">
      <xsl:text>titleText</xsl:text>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="x">
      <xsl:value-of select="$Ax"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:attribute name="y">

```

```

        <xsl:value-of select="$0y + 5"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:value-of select="$shelfmark"/>
    <xsl:text> - </xsl:text>
    <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="$detected eq 0">
            <xsl:text>endleaves not detected</xsl:text>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:otherwise>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="concat(upper-case(substring($side,1,1)),
                    substring($side, 2),
                    '[not(last())]
                )"/>
            <xsl:text> endleaves (</xsl:text>
            <xsl:value-of
                select="concat(upper-case(substring($use,1,1)),
                    substring($use, 2),
                    '[not(last())]
                )"/>
            <xsl:text></xsl:text>
        </xsl:otherwise>
    </xsl:choose>
</text>
</xsl:template>

<!-- Description -->
<xsl:template name="description">
    <xsl:param name="baseline"/>
    <xsl:param name="unknown"/>
    <xsl:variable name="baseline" select="$baseline - 10"/>
    <g xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:attribute name="class">
            <xsl:text>descText</xsl:text>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:choose>
            <xsl:when test="no | NC | NK | other">
                <text xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                    <xsl:attribute name="x">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$0x + 20"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                    <xsl:attribute name="y">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                    <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                        <xsl:choose>
                            <xsl:when test="no">
                                <xsl:text>There are no endleaves</xsl:text>
                            </xsl:when>
                            <xsl:otherwise>
                                <xsl:text>Endleaves not described</xsl:text>
                            </xsl:otherwise>
                        </xsl:choose>
                    </tspan>
                </text>
            </xsl:when>
            <xsl:when test="$unknown eq 'other'">
                <text xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                    <xsl:attribute name="x">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$0x + 20"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                    <xsl:attribute name="y">
                        <xsl:value-of select="$baseline"/>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                    <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">

```

```

        <xsl:value-of select="./yes/type/other/text()"/>
    </tspan>
</text>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
    <xsl:value-of select="$unknown"/>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
<xsl:for-each select="yes/type">
    <xsl:variable name="position" select="position()"/>
    <text xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
        <xsl:attribute name="x">
            <xsl:value-of select="$0x + 20"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:attribute name="y">
            <xsl:value-of select="$baseline"/>
        </xsl:attribute>
        <xsl:for-each select="separate">
            <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                <xsl:attribute name="dy">
                    <xsl:value-of select="0 + 6 * ($position - 1)"/>
                </xsl:attribute>
                <xsl:text>Separate endleaves: </xsl:text>
                <xsl:for-each select="units/unit">
                    <xsl:variable name="position" select="position()"/>

                    <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                        <xsl:attribute name="x">
                            <xsl:value-of select="$0x + 80"/>
                        </xsl:attribute>
                        <xsl:attribute name="dy">
                            <xsl:value-of select="if ($position eq 1)
then 0 else 7"/>
                        </xsl:attribute>
                        <xsl:text>unit </xsl:text>
                        <xsl:value-of select="position()"/>
                        <xsl:text>: </xsl:text>
                        <xsl:for-each select="components/component">
                            <xsl:variable name="position" select="posi-
tion()"/>

                            <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
                                <xsl:attribute name="x">
                                    <xsl:attribute name="x">
                                        <xsl:value-of select="$0x + 100"/>
                                    </xsl:attribute>
                                </xsl:attribute>
                                <xsl:attribute name="dy">
                                    <xsl:value-of
select="if ($position eq 1) then
0 else 7"/>
                                </xsl:attribute>
                                <xsl:text>component </xsl:text>
                                <xsl:value-of select="position()"/>
                                <xsl:text>: </xsl:text>
                            <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">

                                <xsl:attribute name="dx">
                                    <xsl:text>2pt</xsl:text>
                                </xsl:attribute>
                                <xsl:choose>
                                    <xsl:when test="type/hook">
                                        <xsl:value-of
lect="type/hook/type/node()/name()"/>

```

```

test="type/hook/node()/double/yes">
other]">
lect="type/node()/name()"/>
| other]">
lect="pastedown/node()/name()"/>
| other]">
er/text()"/>
al/node()/name()"/>
tp://www.w3.org/2000/svg"

<xsl:choose>
  <xsl:when
    <xsl:text> double</xsl:text>
  </xsl:when>
</xsl:choose>
</xsl:when>
  <xsl:when test="type[NC | NK |
    <xsl:text>type </xsl:text>
  <xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="type/NC">
      <xsl:text>not checked</xsl:text>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="type/NK">
      <xsl:text>not known</xsl:text>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="type/other">
      <xsl:text>other</xsl:text>
    </xsl:when>
  </xsl:choose>
</xsl:when>
<xsl:otherwise>
  <xsl:value-of se-
    </xsl:otherwise>
  </xsl:choose>
<xsl:text> (</xsl:text>
<xsl:choose>
  <xsl:when test="pastedown/yes">
    <xsl:text> pastedown, </xsl:text>
  </xsl:when>
  <xsl:when test="pastedown[NC | NK
    <xsl:text> pastedown: </xsl:text>
  <xsl:value-of se-
    <xsl:text>, </xsl:text>
  </xsl:when>
</xsl:choose>
<xsl:choose>
  <xsl:when test="material[NC | NK
    <xsl:text>material: </xsl:text>
  <xsl:choose>
    <xsl:when test="material/NC">
      <xsl:text>not checked</xsl:text>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="material/NK">
      <xsl:text>not known</xsl:text>
    </xsl:when>
    <xsl:when test="material/other">
      <xsl:value-of select="material/oth-
    </xsl:when>
  </xsl:choose>
  <xsl:text>, </xsl:text>
  </xsl:when>
</xsl:otherwise>
  <xsl:value-of select="materi-
    <tspan xmlns="ht-

```

```

dx="-1pt">
  <xsl:text>, </xsl:text>
</tspan>
</xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
<xsl:choose>
  <xsl:when test="attachment[NC |
NK | other]">
    <xsl:text>attachment: </xsl:text>

    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="attachment/NC">
        <xsl:text>not checked</xsl:text>
      </xsl:when>
      <xsl:when test="attachment/NK">
        <xsl:text>not known</xsl:text>
      </xsl:when>
      <xsl:when test="attachment/other">
        <xsl:value-of select="attachment/oth-
er/text()"/>
      </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
  </xsl:when>
  <xsl:otherwise>
    <xsl:value-of select="attach-
ment/node()/name()"/>
  </xsl:otherwise>
</xsl:choose>
<tspan xmlns="ht-
tp://www.w3.org/2000/svg" dx="0pt">
  <xsl:text></xsl:text>
</tspan>
</tspan>
</tspan>
</tspan>
</xsl:for-each>
</xsl:for-each>
</tspan>
</xsl:for-each>
<xsl:for-each select="integral">
  <xsl:variable name="position"
    select="if ($position eq 1) then 1 else 1.5 +
count(parent::type/preceding-sibling::type/separate/units/unit/components/compon-
ent)"/>
  <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
    <xsl:attribute name="dy">
      <xsl:value-of select="concat(0 + 6 * ($position -
1), 'pt')"/>
    </xsl:attribute>
    <xsl:text>Integral endleaves: </xsl:text>
    <tspan xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg">
      <xsl:attribute name="x">
        <xsl:value-of select="$0x + 80"/>
      </xsl:attribute>
      <xsl:value-of select="numberOfLeaves"/>
    </tspan>
    <xsl:choose>
      <xsl:when test="xs:integer(numberOfLeaves) gt
1">
        <xsl:text> leaves</xsl:text>
      </xsl:when>
      <xsl:otherwise>
        <xsl:text> leaf</xsl:text>
      </xsl:otherwise>
    </xsl:choose>
  </tspan>

```

```

                <xsl:choose>
                    <xsl:when test="pastedown/yes">
                        <xsl:text> (pastedown)</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:when>
                </xsl:choose>
            </tspan>
        </tspan>
    </xsl:for-each>
</text>
</xsl:for-each>
</g>
</xsl:template>

<!-- Uncertainty template -->
<xsl:template name="certainty">
    <xsl:param name="certainty" select="100" as="xs:integer"/>
    <xsl:param name="uncertaintyIncrement"/>
    <xsl:param name="type"/>
    <xsl:choose>
        <xsl:when test="$type = '1'">
            <xsl:choose>
                <xsl:when test="$certainty lt 100">
                    <xsl:attribute name="filter">
                        <xsl:text>url(#f1)</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                </xsl:when>
            </xsl:choose>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="$type = '2'">
            <xsl:choose>
                <xsl:when test="$certainty lt 100">
                    <xsl:attribute name="filter">
                        <xsl:text>url(#f2)</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                </xsl:when>
            </xsl:choose>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="$type = '3'">
            <xsl:choose>
                <xsl:when test="$certainty lt 100">
                    <xsl:attribute name="filter">
                        <xsl:text>url(#f3)</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                </xsl:when>
            </xsl:choose>
        </xsl:when>
        <xsl:when test="$type = '4'">
            <xsl:choose>
                <xsl:when test="$certainty lt 100">
                    <xsl:attribute name="filter">
                        <xsl:text>url(#f4)</xsl:text>
                    </xsl:attribute>
                </xsl:when>
            </xsl:choose>
        </xsl:when>
    </xsl:choose>
</xsl:template>

</xsl:stylesheet>

```

Endleaf master SVG

This section contains the master SVG coding written for this project for endleaf transformations. This particular file makes available to the XSLT stylesheet a series of filters and shaped masks to be applied when needed to endleaf diagrams.

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<?xml-stylesheet href="../../CSS/style.css" type="text/css"?>
<!DOCTYPE svg
PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD SVG 1.1//EN" "http://www.w3.org/Graphics/SVG/1.1/DTD/svg11.dtd">
<svg xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2000/svg" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink"
version="1.1"
x="0" y="0" width="297mm" height="210mm" viewBox="0 0 297 210"
preserveAspectRatio="xMinYMin meet">
<defs>
<filter id="f1" filterUnits="userSpaceOnUse">
<feColorMatrix in="SourceGraphic" type="matrix" values="
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.6 0.0"/>
<feGaussianBlur stdDeviation="0.5 0.1"/>
</filter>
<filter id="f2" filterUnits="userSpaceOnUse">
<feColorMatrix in="SourceGraphic" type="matrix" values="
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.65 0.0"/>
<feGaussianBlur stdDeviation="0.5 0.3"/>
</filter>
<filter id="f3" filterUnits="userSpaceOnUse">
<feColorMatrix in="SourceGraphic" type="matrix" values="
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.65 0.0"/>
<feGaussianBlur stdDeviation="0.5"/>
</filter>
<filter id="f4" filterUnits="userSpaceOnUse">
<feColorMatrix in="SourceGraphic" type="matrix" values="
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
0.0 0.0 0.0 0.65 0.0"/>
<feGaussianBlur stdDeviation="0 0.5"/>
</filter>
<linearGradient id="fading">
<stop offset="0%" stop-color="#FFFFFF"/>
<stop offset="50%" stop-color="#666666"/>
<stop offset="90%" stop-color="#000000"/>
</linearGradient>
<linearGradient id="fading2">
<stop offset="0%" stop-color="#000000"/>
<stop offset="50%" stop-color="#666666"/>
<stop offset="90%" stop-color="#FFFFFF"/>
</linearGradient>
<radialGradient id="radialFading">
<stop offset="0%" stop-color="#FFFFFF"/>
<stop offset="50%" stop-color="#666666"/>
<stop offset="90%" stop-color="#000000"/>
</radialGradient>
<g id="outermostGL">
<desc>Outermost gathering Left</desc>
<path d="M 140,0 L 10,0 A 10,10 0 0,0 10,20 L 140,20 z"/>
</g>
<pattern id="gluedPattern" patternUnits="userSpaceOnUse" x="2" y="0" width="5"
height="10"
viewBox="0 0 10 10" xlink:type="simple" xlink:show="other" xlink:actu-
ate="onLoad"

```

```

        preserveAspectRatio="xMidYMid meet">
        <desc>Glue pattern</desc>
        <path d="M 0,5 L 3,0 " class="glued"/>
    </pattern>
    <pattern id="gluedPattern2" patternUnits="userSpaceOnUse" x="0" y="0"
width="8" height="8">
        <g fill="none" class="glued" stroke-linecap="round">
            <g stroke="#888888" stroke-width="0.5">
                <path d="M0,0 L8,8"/>
                <path d="M2,0 L8,6"/>
                <path d="M4,0 L8,4"/>
                <path d="M6,0 L8,2"/>
                <path d="M8,0 L8,0"/>
                <path d="M0,2 L6,8"/>
                <path d="M0,4 L4,8"/>
                <path d="M0,6 L2,8"/>
                <path d="M0,8 L0,8"/>
            </g>
        </g>
    </pattern>
    <g id="pastedown" class="line" stroke-linecap="round">
        <desc>pastedown</desc>
        <path d="M 0,0 L 130,0"/>
        <rect width="130" height="5" fill="url(#gluedPattern)" stroke-opa-
city="0.0"/>
    </g>
    <rect id="pasted" width="130" height="5" fill="url(#gluedPattern)" stroke-
opacity="0.0"/>
    <clipPath id="guardClip">
        <rect id="rect1" width="32.5" height="10" x="97.5" y="-2"
style="stroke: gray; fill: none;"/>
    </clipPath>
    <clipPath id="outsideHookClip">
        <rect id="rect12" width="16.25" height="10" x="113.75" y="-2"
style="stroke: gray; fill: none;"/>
    </clipPath>
</defs>

    <!-- Call the definitions above inside the groups below by <use xlink:href="#+ID
here]", use the X and Y attributes of the use element to move the components around
-->

</svg>

```

Endleaf CSS

This section contains the CSS code written for this project to rule the appearance of lines within endleaf diagrams.

```

/* style.css */

/*
 *   GENERAL   *
 *
 * stroke=#000000; stroke-width=1; fill=none;
 */

.titleText{
    font-family: 'SimonciniGaramond LT', garamond, serif;
    font-style: normal;
    font-weight: bold;
    font-size: 10pt;
    dominant-baseline: alphabetic;
    text-anchor: middle;
}

.descText{
    font-family: 'SimonciniGaramond LT', garamond, serif;
    font-style: normal;
    font-weight: normal;
    font-size: 5pt;
    dominant-baseline: alphabetic;
    text-anchor: start;
}

.line{
    stroke:#000000;
    stroke-width:1pt;
    fill:none;
}

.line2{
    stroke:#000000;
    stroke-width:2pt;
    fill:none;
}

.line_ref{
    stroke:#999999;
    stroke-width:0.5pt;
    fill:none;
}

.thread{
    stroke:#000000;
    stroke-width:0.5;
    fill:none;
}

```